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SOME PROBLEMATIC ISSUES OF THE APPLICATION OF INTERNATIONAL HUMANITARIAN LAW

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the basics of compliance with the provisions of international humanitarian law and compensation for harm caused as a result of violations of international humanitarian law, examines the problems that arise in compensation for harm, reveals the types of compensation and support. The paper analyzes numerous agreements related to the protection of civilians during armed conflicts. Much attention is paid to the issue related to the lack of a mechanism for pre-trial compensation for damage caused as a result of violations of international humanitarian law. The conclusion is made about the need for further steps towards the codification and progressive development of international humanitarian law, strengthening the regime of implementation of its norms applied in conditions of international and non-international armed conflicts.*

Keywords: *war, armed conflict, the warring party, damage, harm, violation of norms, protection.*

In the current conditions, due to the emergence of increasingly acute contradictions and armed conflicts between States, the topic of the application of international humanitarian law (IHL) does not lose its relevance. The norms of international humanitarian law, which establish restrictions on the use of a number of methods and means of combating the enemy in the course of warfare, have been formed throughout world history.

In modern conditions, the problems of compliance and application of international humanitarian law have become particularly acute in connection with the armed conflicts arising in various regions of our planet.

The objective basis of this branch of international law is an armed conflict between States and their mutual obligations regarding the regulation of the situation of certain persons in such a conflict.

The regulation of hostilities is carried out in IHL in such a way as to limit their brutality and ensure humanitarian standards for combatants, prisoners of war, the wounded, the sick, as well as the civilian population.

According to the doctrine of international law, peremptory norms constitute the general international law and require their unconditional fulfillment due to the fact that they belong to the norms of jus cogens, since they are created by the entire international community [1, p. 15]. Such imperative norms include the basic principles of international law, which were enshrined in the UN Charter of 1945, the Declaration on Principles of International Law of 1970, the Helsinki Act of 1975, the Declaration of Principles Governing Relations between member States of the 1999 Conference on Interaction and Confidence-Building Measures in Asia, etc. One of these principles is the "non-use of force or threat of force" in international relations between States and other subjects of international law. However, after the adoption of the UN Charter, where this principle was reflected for the first time, there was probably not a single year when this principle was not violated. Obviously, this served as one of the Basic ideas of IHL is the idea of humanism, respect for the dignity of the human person, and the inadmissibility of violating its fundamental rights and freedoms.

In a broad sense, this concept includes other institutions of international law: human rights, international security law, etc. Like any branch of law, it has the necessary set of norms, both imperative and dispositive, that regulate the relations of participants in armed conflicts. The main

goal of this branch of international law is to reduce the suffering caused to all people by wars as much as possible.

Currently, the rules of warfare are being consolidated in international treaties concluded between States. Over time, the relationship between States regarding the conduct of hostilities, the protection of civilians, and the use of new types of weapons has become impossible to regulate only by internal acts, separate agreements that would be concluded between such States. It was necessary to look for new opportunities to create a common, unified mechanism for the settlement of relations between States in armed conflicts.

International humanitarian law generally meets the requirements of modern international relations, but there are problems that require some improvement. In particular, improving the effectiveness of IHL, protecting civilians during military operations.

Today, the regulatory framework of international humanitarian law has been practically created, but not all international treaties concluded in this field are implemented by States.

One of the main problems is the lack of an institution for the exchange of prisoners of war. Despite the fact that such an institution exists in practice, it has not yet received legal consolidation. The consolidation of such an institution and the legal regulation of the rules for the exchange of prisoners of war will improve the provisions of the Geneva Convention on the Treatment of Prisoners of War.

Given the emergence and proliferation of new types of weapons and methods of warfare, the need to study and comply with the norms of IHL is beyond doubt.

The topic of sufficiency of existing IHL norms to regulate modern armed conflicts is relevant. We emphasize the blurring of the time and geographical framework of modern armed conflicts, the emergence of new participants (for example, private military and security companies) and technologies (unmanned aerial vehicles, cyber weapons). Increasingly, we have to talk about asymmetric wars, when the lack of funds is compensated by the methods of use.

The institution of international legal responsibility and compensation for harm is of paramount importance not only for the field of international law, but also plays a key role in ensuring peace, order and stability throughout the world.

Currently, there is no mechanism for pre-trial resolution of issues of compensation for damage caused as a result of violations of international humanitarian law. The State must compensate for damage to property during military operations.

Terrorist methods can accompany military operations, then they certainly fall under the scope of IHL. In order to ensure the protection of the civilian population, numerous conventions have been adopted over the past fifty years concerning part of the rules of engagement. Despite this, modern realities show that the majority of victims of armed conflicts are civilians (75-80% of the total number of victims). In the context of modern military conflicts, such casualties are not just the costs of war, they are caused by deliberate actions against the civilian population.

Some norms of international conventions governing the rules of warfare and assistance to the wounded and injured are difficult to understand. In accordance with the norms of international conventions, the party in whose hands the bodies of the dead soldiers of the enemy turned out to be is obliged to carry out all ritual procedures in accordance with religious canons and humanity.

Diplomatic immunity is one of the main institutions of international law. Attacks on ambassadors are not uncommon in our time either. We have received reports from various news sources about the attack on ambassadors and consular offices. The reason for such international offenses is the low legal culture of the population.

It must be remembered that the territory of the consulate and embassy is actually a foreign territory.

The Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court, which entered into force on July 1, 2002, banned the recruitment and recruitment of minors at the international level. According to paragraph 2 (b) (xxvi) of article 8, "it is an offence to recruit or recruit minors under the age of 15 into armed forces or groups or to use them for active participation in hostilities during international armed

conflicts" [2]. In addition, paragraph 2 (e) (vii) of article 8 contains a similar prohibition in relation to non-international conflicts.

Article 52 of the Geneva Convention on the Fate of the Wounded and Sick in Active Armies of 1949 provides a norm according to which it is prohibited to commit attacks of an indiscriminate nature affecting the civilian population or civilian objects [3]. In any case, the warring parties should keep in mind two fundamental principles when using weapons: expediency and necessity.

It is well known that during the Second World War, Nazi German officers treated prisoners of war inhumanely. According to the Geneva Convention on the Treatment of Prisoners of War of 1949, persons held captive by an enemy State have many rights. According to article 25 of this Convention, the conditions for the placement of prisoners of war in camps must be the same as those enjoyed by the troops of the captive Power [4]. Unfortunately, these standards are not being observed at the present time.

The problem of using human shields to achieve military success was faced by American soldiers during the American-Iraqi war. Iraqi insurgents used human shields under threats to the civilian population. Because of this, the NATO military was practically deprived of the opportunity to conduct military operations. IHL in the Geneva Convention relative to the Protection of Civilian Persons in Time of War of 1949 requires the parties to the conflict to distinguish between the civilian population and direct participants in hostilities in order to ensure the protection of the civilian population and civilian objects [5]. There are disputes regarding the participation of citizens in human shields voluntarily. The use of human shields cannot be considered an act of military cunning, because hundreds of lives are in mortal danger.

The cessation of the existence of one State and the emergence of new entities in its place in accordance with the right to self-determination is rarely complete without armed violence, human casualties and serious destruction. Evidence of this is the collapse of the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia (SFRY), which, in our opinion, took place according to the worst possible scenario in such a situation, accompanied by a series of armed conflicts characterized by extreme cruelty, which cannot be justified either by the exercise of the right to self-determination or by the desire to preserve the territorial integrity of the State. Extensive documentary and analytical material, including a significant number of publications by domestic and foreign researchers, contains a variety of, often diametrically opposed approaches to determining the causes of the Yugoslav crisis, burdened by a chain of interrelated armed conflicts of an international and non-international nature, during which gross and massive violations of the norms and principles of international humanitarian law were committed [6, p. 982]. During the conflict and NATO bombing in Yugoslavia, about 10,000 people (mainly Albanians) died. About a million people have become refugees and displaced persons.

Most of the Albanian refugees, unlike the Serb refugees, have returned to their homes. The total number of victims of conflicts in the Balkans since the early 1990s exceeds 130 thousand people.

The material damage amounts to tens of billions of dollars. The civilian population and the welfare of Yugoslavia turned out to be, to use the terminology of the Pentagon, "collateral victims" of the NATO operation against Milosevic's army. As a result of the NATO humanitarian intervention in Yugoslavia, 2.5 thousand civilians were killed, including children, 12.5 thousand people were injured (and this is not to mention military losses). The exact number of victims of those events has not yet been named.

48 hospitals, 128 industrial and service facilities, 89 factories and plants, 82 bridges, dozens of tunnels and road junctions, more than 100 television and radio towers and repeaters, 64 churches and monasteries, numerous cultural facilities, more than a hundred buildings of universities, schools and kindergartens were destroyed. The total material damage, according to various estimates, amounted to \$ 30-100 billion. The NATO armed forces carried out about 4,000 strikes on the territory of Serbia and Montenegro, while they used depleted uranium ammunition and attacked oil and chemical industry facilities. The outbreak of cancer in the bombed areas has become another legacy of the NATO operation to protect the civilian population of Serbia from the "Milosevic regime" [7, p. 141].

Thus, according to the recognition of human rights organizations affiliated with the West (Amnesty International and Human Rights Watch), hundreds of incidents of that period fall under the category of war crimes.

The fact that NATO bombed a country in the center of Europe without a UN mandate became an attempt on international law and a precedent that opened the way for further aggression in Iraq, Libya, and Syria.

In 2017, Serbia announced the preparation of lawsuits against 19 NATO countries involved in the bombing. Specialists in the field of medicine, physics, chemistry, as well as international lawyers from Germany, France, Italy, Russia, China, Great Britain and Turkey worked on the collection of materials necessary for the prosecution.

Compensation for damage caused to the health of citizens of the country attacked by NATO is at the heart of most lawsuits. The first lawsuits from Serbian citizens suffering from cancer have already begun.

NATO countries will be sued for compensation for material and moral damage. So far, these are five countries of the military bloc. Most consider this idea of filing lawsuits against NATO to be viable, albeit belated. In 2004, Serbia and Montenegro (then a single state) filed a lawsuit against eight NATO countries in the International Court of Justice – Great Britain, the United States, Belgium, Canada, France, Germany, Italy, Spain, the Netherlands and Portugal.

After two public hearings, the judges found that The Hague did not have jurisdiction over the claims of Yugoslavia against Spain and the United States.

On this basis, the court did not consider claims against other countries either. The fact remains indisputable that both the Council of Europe, the CSCE, and the UN were unable to prevent armed violence in the former Yugoslavia and the massive crimes that were committed there. However, these crimes were of such a large scale and were distinguished by such cruelty that the community of States represented by the United Nations could not remain indifferent. Violations of international humanitarian law regarding the use of the practice of "ethnic cleansing" on the territory of Yugoslavia on July 13 and August 13, 1992 were discussed at the 3093 and 3106 meetings of the UN Security Council. The Commission concluded that large-scale vectorization had taken place in the territory of the former Yugoslavia, stipulating that it had not always had the opportunity to verify the reliability of the facts.

Despite this, all parties to the conflict are obliged to comply with international humanitarian law, in particular the Geneva Conventions of August 12, 1949, and those who violate or order the violation of these Conventions are personally responsible for these violations.

A significant contribution of the International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia (ICTY) to the practice of international criminal justice has been the concretization of elements of personal criminal responsibility.

Since its founding in 1993, the ICTY has formally indicted 161 people (including more than 90 against Serbs, about 30 against Croats, 8 against Kosovo Albanians, 7 against Bosnian Muslims and 2 against Macedonians). At the same time, his guilt has not been proven. The accused at the trial in The Hague was former Yugoslav President Slobodan Milosevic, who died in prison in 2006. At the same time, his guilt has not been proven [8, p. 47].

The era of ad hoc UN ad hoc tribunals, whose work lasted for more than 20 years and cost more than billions of dollars (funds that could, according to some researchers, be more usefully used, for example, for the needs of victims), has ended. They were replaced by the International Criminal Court and the so-called hybrid or mixed courts and tribunals, international criminal justice bodies, which largely owe their appearance to the ad hoc Tribunals.

As we can see, the helplessness of the former legal institutions and the weakness of the established international system are evident.

So, in 1990, when Iraq attacked Kuwait and the UN Security Council adopted several resolutions aimed at restoring the status quo, in none of them did it use its powers and did not recognize Iraq as the aggressor.

In 2018, when the armed forces of the United States, France and the United Kingdom, grossly violating the sovereignty of Syria, fired missiles at its territory under a far-fetched pretext, resulting in material damage and the death of citizens, the reaction of the UN in the person of the Secretary-General was surprisingly mild. It seems that he forgot that in accordance with the UN General Assembly resolution of December 14, 1974, an act of aggression is considered "... the use of any weapon by a state against the territory of another state" [9].

The primary responsibility for the maintenance of international peace and security lies with the Security Council. Surprisingly, the organization, which is designed to mobilize all the efforts of the international community not only to prevent military action, but also to provide assistance to victims of such arbitrariness, instead develops a secret directive "Parameters and principles of the UN assistance to Syria."

It follows from the document that the assistance of international organizations in the reconstruction of the country is possible only after a change of government. At the same time, it prohibits countries from participating in any projects to restore the Syrian economy. Today, the international security system needs to be seriously adjusted. It is necessary to develop new mechanisms to guarantee peaceful coexistence for countries and peoples in the 21st century. The issue of the theoretical foundations of international law is acute, because the peremptory norms and principles of international law have lost their imperativeness.

Today, the international legal prohibition of wars and armed conflicts does not mean their complete prevention. Therefore, international humanitarian law will continue to be the main regulator of public relations that develop during armed conflicts. Consequently, further steps are required to codify and progressively develop international humanitarian law, strengthen the regime of implementation of its norms applied in situations of international and non-international armed conflicts, including in cases of internationalization of the latter. There are many reasons why additional norms of international law have been developed.

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